

First record of *Lanchnophorus singalensis* (Dohrn, 1860) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae) in Cyprus

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ABSTRACT: The first record of *Lanchnophorus singalensis* (Dohrn, 1860) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Rhyparochromini) in Cyprus is reported. Information on the known distribution of *L. singalensis* is summarised.

KEY WORDS: *Lanchnophorus singalensis*, alien species, first record, distribution, Cyprus, Mediterranean Region.

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Lanchnophorus singalensis (Dohrn, 1860) Now, *L. singalensis* can be reported from (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae: Cyprus: On 22.09.2023, an adult specimen Rhyparochrominae: Rhyparochromini) is (Fig. 1) was found and photographed on a mainly distributed in Africa, the Arabian balcony on the 4th floor of a building in Peninsula, Pakistan and India and less the capital Nicosia (Semen Pavlenov, common in the Oriental Region east of pers. comm.). Four photographs of the India (Kment et al., 2017). specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Pavlenov, 2023).

In the Mediterranean Region, *L. singalensis* has been reported from Egypt and Lebanon, Up to now, *L. singalensis* has not been so far (Kment et al., 2017; Matocq & reported from Cyprus. Thus, the record Azar, 2023). reported herein is the first one for this country.

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REFERENCES

- Kment, P., Carapezza, A., Jindra, Z., Kondorosy, E., 2017, Review of the genus *Lanchnophorus* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae) with description of three new species and other nomenclatural changes, *Zootaxa*, 4226(1): 47-74.
- Matocq, A., Azar, D., 2023, Preliminary inventory of terrestrial Heteroptera from Lebanon (Hemiptera: Leptopodomorpha, Cimicomorpha and Pentatomomorpha), *Zootaxa*, 5230(1): 1-26.
- Pavlenov, S., 2023, *Lanchnophorus singalensis*. Photographs to be found on iNaturalist [Online database]. Available from: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/184377565>. (Accessed: 03.03.2024).

Figure 1. Specimen of *Lanchnophorus singalensis* (Dohrn, 1860), Nicosia, Cyprus, 22.09.2023. (Photo: Semen Pavlenov).